

Use cases of OpenAIRE Open Science services for different stakeholders

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	Name	Organisation	Date
From	Iryna Kuchma	EIFL	30/11/2018
Edited by	Paula Moura André Vieira Angelica Vos	UMINHO UMINHO ATHENA	18/12/2018
Reviewed by	Najla Rettberg Pedro Príncipe	UGOE UMINHO	21/12/2018
Approved by	Pedro Príncipe	UMINHO	08/01/2019
For delivery	Mike Hatzopoulos	UOA	09/01/2019

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Publishable Summary

OpenAIRE carries out training activities on its Open Science services and tools in collaboration with OpenAIRE-Connect project targeting researchers and project coordinators, research managers, research communities and research infrastructures, data librarians, content providers, innovators and funders. These training activities profile OpenAIRE services, describe their scenarios targeted at different users and provide use cases of how they are used. This report includes an overview of 14 OpenAIRE services for researchers and project coordinators, research communities, research managers and funders, innovators and content providers and nine use cases covering the following:

- [Amnesia](#): a flexible data anonymization tool that allows to remove identifying information from data
- [Data2Paper](#) Scholix Integration
- Enabling open science publishing for Research Infrastructures: [The EPOS use-case](#)
- [Matchbook](#): A new recommender service to spark scientific collaboration
- [OpenAIRE APIs](#) and Open Science Management at ISCTE – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa
- [Open, interoperable and reproducible neuroinformatics](#) with Research Community Dashboard
- Tracking, reporting, monitoring: [FWF - Austrian Science Fund use case](#)
- [VIPER](#): The Visual Project Explorer
- [Zenodo](#): A universal repository for all your research outcomes

Amnesia and Zenodo use cases have been developed in collaboration with EOSC-Hub project.

1. OPENAIRE SERVICES FOR OPEN SCIENCE

OpenAIRE provides the following services and tools for Open Science:

1.1 OpenAIRE Discovery Portal: Find open linked research

<https://explore.openaire.eu>

The OpenAIRE Discovery portal provides access to research content. It is based on OpenAIRE's open scholarly communication graph that includes all research and scholarly activities, spanning all phases of the research life cycle (see more details below under OpenAIRE Graph: Open, linked research). In addition to the usual search and browse mechanisms, the OpenAIRE Discovery portal provides end user functionalities which allow users to find the most fitting repository to deposit their publication or data, authoritatively enrich the underlying content (e.g., linking research results to funding, linking research results to external sources), view, download reports or graphs of aggregated research outcomes (e.g., per funder, project, institution) and their stats.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL: Actual system proven in operational environment

LIFECYCLE STATUS: Production

TARGET USERS: Academic and research communities, policy makers, funders, research libraries, educators, industry, citizen scientists and public.

USER VALUE

- Enables intelligent and contextualized research discovery.
- Connects public to open access research in Europe and beyond.

USER BASE: 9,200 registered users. 50,000 users use the service on the average every month.

1.2 Amnesia: Anonymize your datasets

<https://amnesia.openaire.eu>

Anonymization

Amnesia allows end users to anonymize sensitive data in order to share them with a broad audience. The user guides the anonymization process and decides on a flexible trade-off between privacy guaranty and data utility. The service is also offered through a web interface that allows users to explore the anonymized data visually. Moreover, the service detects duplicate anonymized files when they are uploaded to Zenodo.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL: System complete and qualified

LIFECYCLE STATUS: Beta

TARGET USERS: Research communities, Research Infrastructures, universities, research centers, hospitals. Any commercial provider that produces data and wants to share them or outsource them.

USER VALUE

- Reduces or eliminates the dangers to the privacy of the users that are associated with the data.
- Allows data owners and curators to safely share the data with other experts and to benefit from their processing on them.

USER BASE: Researchers, data providers

What it is

[Amnesia](#) is a flexible data anonymization tool that allows to remove identifying information from data. Amnesia transforms relational and transactional data to anonymized datasets where formal privacy guaranties hold. It does not only remove direct identifiers like names, SSNs, etc., but also transforms secondary identifiers like birth date and zip code so that **individuals cannot be identified in the data**, by linking them to other sources of information.

What it does

Amnesia implements data anonymization techniques from the field of Privacy Preserving Data Publishing (PPDP). The key idea in anonymization is that identifying information is removed from the published data, so that sensitive information cannot be attributed to a person.

Anonymization techniques present descriptive information in an obscure or generalized way, to guarantee that such associations cannot take place. Anonymization algorithms transform the data into a form that provides a privacy guarantee with the minimum possible distortion of the original data. A significant challenge for every anonymization method is to provide the best trade-off between privacy guaranty strength and anonymized data quality.

Amnesia supports k-anonymity and k^m -anonymity, two privacy guaranties that make each record indistinguishable from other k-1 records. Original data are anonymized by using generalization

and suppression. Generalization is the substitution of a value in the original file, e.g., "Athens" with a more abstract one, e.g., "Greece". Substitutions take place according to a predefined hierarchy of values, e.g., "Athens" < "Greece" < "Europe", which is user defined or it can be automatically created by the tool.

Amnesia offers algorithms that take advantage of modern hardware architectures that feature multiple computer cores. Moreover, Amnesia allows the user to guide the anonymization process by visualizing the candidate solutions and allowing the user to choose and customize the most convenient one.

ID	Age	Zipcode	Diagnosis
1	28	13053	Heart Disease
2	29	13068	Heart Disease
3	21	13068	Viral Infection
4	23	13053	Viral Infection
5	50	14853	Cancer
6	55	14853	Heart Disease
7	47	14850	Viral Infection
8	49	14850	Viral Infection
9	31	13053	Cancer
10	37	13053	Cancer
11	36	13222	Cancer
12	35	13068	Cancer

k-anonymization

ID	Age	Zipcode	Diagnosis
1	[20-30]	130**	Heart Disease
2	[20-30]	130**	Heart Disease
3	[20-30]	130**	Viral Infection
4	[20-30]	130**	Viral Infection
5	[40-60]	148**	Cancer
6	[40-60]	148**	Heart Disease
7	[40-60]	148**	Viral Infection
8	[40-60]	148**	Viral Infection
9	[30-40]	13***	Cancer
10	[30-40]	13***	Cancer
11	[30-40]	13***	Cancer
12	[30-40]	13***	Cancer

Original and anonymized dataset with k=4

The user can explore the quality of the data with ad hoc queries and a visual representation of the value distribution. He can choose to suppress outliers in order to avoid unnecessary generalization of the original data and information loss. Amnesia focuses on usability and flexibility to allow the user to understand and guide the anonymization process. Since anonymization methods have not been extensively used in practice, it is essential that users will be able to tailor the anonymization processes and especially the information loss in the anonymized data to their needs. For more details, you can check our [documentation](#).

How can I use it?

Amnesia is available both as an [online service](#) and as a [local application](#).

Technical Requirements

Amnesia is a web based or desktop application that uses a Java backend to implement the data anonymization algorithm. It runs both in Windows and Linux and requires Java version 8 or greater.

More information

Amnesia: Data anonymization made easy - [slides](#) and [webinar](#) recordings.

<https://www.openaire.eu/amnesia-guide>

1.3 Zenodo: A catch-all repository

<https://zenodo.org>

Zenodo is a general purpose repository that enables researchers, scientists, projects and institutions to share, preserve and showcase multidisciplinary research results (data, software and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. It is founded in the trustworthy CERN data center.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL: Actual system proven in operational environment

LIFECYCLE STATUS: Production

TARGET USERS: Researchers, research communities, project coordinators/principal investigators

USER VALUE: Enables everyone to participate in open science.

USER BASE: Used by researchers and communities all over the world.

What it is

With Zenodo it is possible to share and preserve publications, data, software and all other scholarship for free in OpenAIRE's trusted repository hosted by CERN

Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>) is an open repository for all scholarship, enabling researchers from all disciplines to share and preserve their research outputs, regardless of size or format. Free to upload and free to access, Zenodo makes scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable and discoverable for the long term. It can be used for those who don't have an appropriate institutional or thematic repository.

What it does

- **Sharing and linking research:** Zenodo provides a rich interface which enables linking research outputs to datasets and funding information.
- **Citable and discoverable:** All uploads get a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to make them easily and uniquely citeable. All open content is harvestable via OAI-PMH by third parties.
- **Supports versioning:** Via a top-level DOI all the different versions of a file are supported.
- **Trusted, reliable, safe:** Data is stored at CERN, which has considerable knowledge and experience operating large scale digital repositories. Data files and metadata are kept in multiple online and offline copies.
- **Includes funding information and makes reporting easier:** Zenodo allows to link uploads to grants from more than 11 funders such as European Commission, National Science Foundation and Wellcome Trust. Zenodo is further integrated into reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via [OpenAIRE](#). Researchers just need

to upload their research to Zenodo, and Zenodo and OpenAIRE will take care of the reporting for them.

- **Includes article level metrics:** Tracks attention for scholarship uploaded.
- **Flexible licensing:** Zenodo encourages to share research as openly as possible to maximize use and re-use of research results. However, we also acknowledge that one size does not fit all. Therefore, we allow for uploading under a variety of different licenses and access levels.
- **Reviewing:** Research materials can set to share with reviewers only, and also embargoed.
- **Software preservation made simple:** Zenodo is integrated with GitHub.
- **Supports FAIR principles:** Zenodo makes data [Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable](#).

How can I use it?

Zenodo is for all researchers, scientific communities and research institutions. It is open to all research outputs regardless of funding source.

Zenodo accepts any file format as well as both positive and negative results.

Zenodo does not impose any requirements on format, size, access restrictions or licence. Quite literally we wish there to be no reason for researchers not to share!

Data, software and other artefacts in support of publications may be the core, but equally welcome are the materials associated with conferences, projects or the institutions themselves, all of which are necessary to understand the scholarly process.

Uploaders are responsible for respecting applicable copyright and license conditions for the files they upload.

Researchers can create and curate their own community for a workshop, project, department, journal, into which they can accept or reject uploads. And consider it their own complete digital repository!

Share your research output in 3 steps!

Zenodo offers simple and easy-to-use data archiving with maximum autonomy. The clear web interface allows to easily upload content in just a few steps.

Using GitHub? [Check out](#) our GitHub integration. Software Preservation Made Simple!

Policies: Content, Access and Reuse, Removal and Longevity policies are available [here](#).

Technical requirements

Total files size limit per record is 50GB (max 100 files). One-time 100GB quota can be requested and granted on a case-by-case basis.

Data stored in the CERN Data Center: Your research output is stored safely for the future in same cloud infrastructure as research data from CERN's [Large Hadron Collider](#) and using CERN's battle-tested repository software [Invenio](#), which is used by some of the world's largest repositories such as [INSPIRE HEP](#) and [CERN Document Server](#).

Open in every sense: Zenodo code is itself open source, and is built on the foundation of the [Invenio](#) digital library which is also open source. The work-in-progress, open issues, and roadmap are shared openly in [GitHub](#), and contributions to any aspect are welcomed from anyone.

All meta data is openly available under a CC0 licence, and all open content is openly accessible through open APIs.

More information about Zenodo infrastructure is available here: <http://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure>.

Need more information?

Check out our Zenodo presentation [here](#).

And check out our [Zotero group](#) for articles mentioning or talking about Zenodo.

<https://www.openaire.eu/zenodo-guide>

1.4 OpenAIRE Graph: Open, linked research

<http://develop.openaire.eu>

The OpenAIRE aggregation service creates the OpenAIRE scholarly communication graph by aggregating metadata from validated data providers, enriching by text mining and inference, and collecting information from end-users. The service makes the graph available via different types of APIs: OAI-PMH, HTTP API, Linked Open Data, SPARQL endpoint. The OpenAIRE scholarly communication graph is created bi-monthly by aggregating, cleaning, transforming and inferring content retrieved from OpenAIRE's European and global network of validated OA data providers.

A stand-alone version of the Aggregation Service is offered for deployment for national or thematic infrastructures.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL: Actual system proven in operational environment

LIFECYCLE STATUS: Production

TARGET USERS: Data providers, publishers, funders, institutions, research infrastructures, policy makers, industry, researchers

USER VALUE:

- A gateway to open research.
- Enables intelligent visibility, access and reusability of research content.
- Enables third-party service developers to realize services for scholarly communication and research analytics.

USER BASE:

APIs are accessed on the average 6,000 times every month. The OpenAIRE Scholarly Communication Graph is indexed by two major Library services (EBSCO and ExLibris) and by the US Department of Energy's [Office of Scientific and Technical Information](https://worldwidescience.org) at <https://worldwidescience.org>.

The standalone version of the Aggregation Service has been deployed in the following national settings: Spain, Poland, Turkey and Argentina.

1.5 OpenAIRE Funder Dashboard: Tracking, reporting, monitoring made easy

<https://monitor.openaire.eu>

Funder Monitoring Dashboard

The Funder Dashboard is built on the OpenAIRE Graph and provides a monitoring and reporting mechanism (including visualization) that allows funders and policy makers to monitor all their funded research outcomes. Additional functionalities include private pages that allow configuration and deployment of on-demand visualization services.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL: System prototype demonstration in operational environment

LIFECYCLE STATUS: Production

TARGET USERS: Funders, policy makers

USER VALUE

- Improved, seamless funding monitoring and impact assessment.
- Funders have access to free, advanced monitoring tools to track their research outputs, produce publications reports, track projects results, funder stats and claiming of links between projects and scholarly objects.

USER BASE: The European Commission uses the current mechanism for monitoring the open access policy. Other European national funders are currently using this as well (e.g. FCT, Portugal, NOW, the Netherlands, and more funders are coming on board).

1.6 OpenAIRE Inference: Text and data mining for scholarly communication

This service performs text mining (entity resolution) on the metadata and the full text of publications and extracts information on the links to projects/grants and funders, data citations or links to entities e.g. links to the Protein Data Bank), software citations, author affiliation, references. Furthermore it classifies publications according to several taxonomies. Results of this service are presented in the OpenAIRE portal.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL: Actual system proven in operational environment

LIFECYCLE STATUS: Production

TARGET USERS: All scholarly communication stakeholders

USER VALUE:

- Improved linked open science.
- Improved research analytics.

- Improved research monitoring and impact assessment.
- Customers get structured metadata related to the publications.
- Funders have access to a list of publications that acknowledge their projects.
- Researchers link their research results.
- Content and data providers enrich their content.

USER BASE: The European Commission uses the current mechanism for monitoring the Open Access policy.

1.7 OpenAIRE Research Analytics: Topic modelling for scholarly communication

Research Analytics

This service identifies and annotates large archives of publications with thematic information, i.e., topics, and then leverage them as a means to link documents with other related information, e.g., authors, grants, and journals. Hence, the service analyzes textual information (e.g., abstracts, content), relational information (e.g., publication citations, authorship network), and varied additional side information (e.g., authors, venues, grants) possibly including taxonomies (e.g., ACM CCS, MeSH) and identifies overlapping entity clusters and related entity-to-cluster memberships, and characterize the clusters with multi-view thematic information (i.e., topics) combining all disparate information sources.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL: System prototype demonstration in operational environment

LIFECYCLE STATUS: Beta

TARGET USERS: policy makers, learned societies, funders, publishers, repository managers, research administrators (institutions), libraries, academic and research communities

USER VALUE:

- Improved research analytics.
- Evidence based decision making.

USER BASE: Used by policy advisors.

1.8 OpenAIRE Content Provider Dashboard: One-stop-shop for sharing, improving and enriching your content

<https://provide.openaire.eu>

The OpenAIRE Content Provider Dashboard is a one-stop-shop web service where data providers (repository, data archive, journal, aggregator, CRIS system) interact with OpenAIRE. It provides the front-end access to many of OpenAIRE's backend services:

1. Register – validate data source against OpenAIRE guidelines (via the OpenAIRE validator); register in OpenAIRE; provide links to content for text and data mining; view history of validations, status of harvesting.
2. Enrich – subscribe and view/receive notifications to enrich the metadata or the content of the data source (via the OpenAIRE Broker).
3. Assess – subscribe to the OpenAIRE Usage statistics service; view aggregated, cleaned usage stats for repository access (COUNTER rules, latest robots.txt).

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL: Actual system proven in operational environment

LIFECYCLE STATUS: Production

TARGET USERS: Repository managers, libraries, data providers, publishers, national aggregators

USER VALUE

- Enhanced repository collections and content for more visibility and access.
- Improved institution memory.
- Better institution research assessment.
- Compliance with funder rules.

USER BASE: 1318 data providers of all types have used the registration and validation service.

1.9 Technical support towards OpenAIRE compliance: OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Provider Managers

Interoperability Guidelines

The OpenAIRE Guidelines are a suite of application profiles designed to allow data providers to make their scholarly outputs visible through the OpenAIRE infrastructure. The profiles are based on established metadata and transfer protocol standards. While the focus of each profile is different, they allow for interlinking and the contextualization of research artefacts.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL: Actual system proven in operational environment

LIFECYCLE STATUS: Production

TARGET USERS: Institutional and thematic repositories, data repositories, data archives, CRIS, journal platforms

USER VALUE

- Enhanced interoperability.
- Provides content (metadata and full text) in a consistent, complete and interoperable way.

USER BASE: Followed in Europe by 900+ data providers (different compatibility levels). Adoption in Latin America (LaReferencia), Mexico, Japan for regional/national infrastructures.

1.10 OpenAIRE Validator

Validator

This service performs validation checks on both the quality of implementation of the OAI-PMH protocol and the conformance of the metadata to the specific schemas. It is a rule based system which also provides an admin panel that allows its users to easily configure the individual validation rules and sets of rules that implement the guidelines. OpenAIRE uses it to validate all its registered data providers (literature repositories, OA publishers, data repositories/archives, aggregators, CRIS systems) to the OpenAIRE guidelines.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL: Actual system proven in operational environment

LIFECYCLE STATUS: Production

TARGET USERS

- As an OpenAIRE installed service: Data/content providers (OA publishers, research libraries, institution CRIS managers, national data services/aggregators, thematic aggregators).
- As a standalone deployment at national and regional aggregators, RIs.

USER VALUE

- Increased interoperability.
- Better visibility.
- National, regional aggregators: compliance to local guidelines.
- OpenAIRE Data providers: Compliance to OpenAIRE guidelines. More visibility of their content.
- Better linking to other communities.

USER BASE

OpenAIRE deployment: 1318 data providers have used the service before they register to OpenAIRE. They use it for continuous validations or updates to new versions of the guidelines. An average of 400 monthly visitors/validations. The Validation service has been deployed also for National and Regional Aggregators like La Referencia (Latin America, 11 countries), Fecyt (Spain), Mincyt (Argentina).

1.11 OpenAIRE Broker: OpenAIRE Literature Notification Broker Service

OA Broker

The Broker service supports the exchange of metadata and content amongst repositories, publishers or aggregators, and the enrichment of repository local metadata. It is a subscription-notification service operating on top of the OpenAIRE ScholGraph, a de-duplicated, enriched, linked, open scholarly communication graph. Repository managers subscribe to notifications (events) of interest via a Web application (provided in the OpenAIRE Data Provider Dashboard).

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL: System complete and qualified

LIFECYCLE STATUS: Beta

TARGET USERS: Repository managers, libraries, data providers, publishers, national aggregators

USER VALUE:

- Enriched repositories for better discoverability.
- Improved institution memory.
- Better institution research assessment.
- OA publisher and content providers compliance with funder rules.

What it is

Content enrichment, one of functionalities from [Dashboard for Content providers](#), is a powerful tool that enables Content providers to enrich research artifacts with additional metadata, through the [OpenAIRE Literature Notification Broker Service](#).

The Broker service supports:

- the exchange of metadata and content amongst repositories, publishers or aggregators, and
- the enrichment of repository local metadata.

It is a subscription-notification service operating on top of the [OpenAIRE Graph](#), a de-duplicated, enriched, linked, open scholarly communication graph. Repository managers subscribe to notifications (events) of interest via a Web application (provided in the [OpenAIRE Content Provider Dashboard](#)).

What it does

With OpenAIRE Literature Broker Service Dashboard, repository managers can

- **Monitor all their repositories**
- **View the results suggested** by the information graph
- **Subscribe to notifications for enrichments and additions**, relevant to their repository, appearing at the OpenAIRE information space graph

Broker Service identifies

- **Missing or additional metadata values:** e.g.,
 - abstracts identified in duplicate publications,
 - subjects identified via classification algorithms,
 - PIDs (PC MID, DOI),
 - linked projects from other funders.
- **Other versions of the publication**
- **Related publications, cited data or software**

Broker service main functionalities:

- **Enrichments and notifications**
 - View notifications to enrich the metadata and the content
- **Content events - enrichments**
 - Types & numbers of notifications for a repository
- **Interactive selection notifications of interest**
 - Tweak and refine events

How can I use it?

Check broker Events

How to find/see the events that may enrich my repository contents?

- Access [Content Provider Dashboard](#) > Content > Events
- Select your data source
- Browse Events: choose and find from the list (more or missing metadata), the events that may enrich your data source

Create Notifications

How to create notifications for specific events?

Access [Content Provider Dashboard](#) > Content > Events

- Select your data source
- Browse events: choose from the list (more or missing metadata), the events from which you want to receive notifications
- Select the option “Subscribe to these events”

Training materials

Webinar [OpenAIRE Dashboard for Content Providers](#)

<https://www.openaire.eu/content-enrichment-guide>

1.12 OpenAIRE Usage Statistics

Usage Analytics

The service tracks, collects and analyzes usage data from the network of OpenAIRE data providers and exploits usage metrics, like downloads and metadata views. Tracking of usage activity is performed by exploiting the Open Source Matomo (former Piwik) analytics platform. In addition, usage statistics reports can be collected from SUSHI-Lite compatible endpoints. The analysis uses the COUNTER rules and the latest robots.txt files as provided by the library and the IT communities.

Taking advantage of OpenAIRE's Graph service de-duplication mechanism, it aggregates/merges usage stats that come from different sources and relate to the same object. Note: The service (currently in beta) will be initially deployed for the OpenAIRE network use, but we envision to provide this in different installations/settings.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL: System complete and qualified

LIFECYCLE STATUS: Beta

TARGET USERS: The service tracks, collects and analyses usage data from the network of OpenAIRE data providers and exploits usage metrics like downloads and metadata views. Tracking of usage activity is performed by exploiting the Open Source Matomo (former Piwik) analytics platform.

USER VALUE: Anonymized and aggregated usage data to improve research impact and assessment.

USER BASE: Currently deployed in 31 literature repositories (Portugal, France, Croatia, Bulgaria).

Usage Statistics – How to track the usage activity of your repository

What it is

[OpenAIRE's Usage Statistic service](#) contributes towards impact evaluation of usage activity in Open Access Repositories. This is realized by the generation of comparable, consistent, standards based usage statistics across publishing platforms that take into account different levels of

scholarly information: the usage of data sources, the usage of individual items in the context of their resource type, the usage of individual web resources or files and the usage of resources among different repositories.

What it does

OpenAIRE's Usage Statistic service uses the **Matomo** Open Source Analytics platform (matomo.org) to track usage activity. It collects and analyzes usage data from the network of OpenAIRE data providers and exploits usage metrics like downloads and metadata views. Tracking of usage activity is performed by exploiting the Open Source Matomo analytics platform. In addition, usage statistics reports can be collected from SUSHI-Lite compatible endpoints.

Statistics are generated using the COUNTER Code of practice directives. The analysis uses the COUNTER rules and the latest robots.txt files as provided by the library and the IT communities. Moreover, and taking advantage of OpenAIRE's Graph service de-duplication mechanism, it aggregates/merges usage stats that come from different sources and relate to the same object.

How can I use it?

Metrics Configuration & Software Details

The service has to be enabled for the repository. This step results in the generation of two unique identifiers:

- a Matomo-ID that associates the repository with its usage events in Matomo platform;
- an authentication-ID that allows to track usage activity on the Matomo platform.

After the generation of the identifiers the repository manager has to perform the following steps:

1. Download the tracking code for the repository platform. The code is maintained on Github:
 - as a patch for various versions of DSpace (<https://github.com/openaire/OpenAIRE-Piwik-DSpace>)
 - as an Eprints plugin for version 3 (<https://github.com/openaire/Eprints-OAPiwik>)
2. Follow the instructions in the code README files and configure the tracker;
3. Deploy the tracking code in the repository.

A notification e-mail will be sent to inform the repository administrator that the installation of the tracking code has been validated and when the usage statistics will be available in the [OpenAIRE Content Provider Dashboard](#).

More information

[OpenAIRE Usage Statistics Guidelines](#)

The guidelines are aimed to provide orientation for data source managers about participation in the OpenAIRE Usage Statistics Service and about the methods and standards used to collect and process usage data in order to generate comparable, standards-based usage statistics. The guidelines follow the Release 4 of the COUNTER Code of Practice for e-Resources supplemented by the IRUS-UK Code of Practice.

<https://www.openaire.eu/guides-usage-statistics>

1.13 Research Community Dashboard

<https://connect.openaire.eu/>

The OpenAIRE Research Community Dashboard is a virtual environment designed for research communities to share and link their research results (literature, datasets, software, other research products, and projects relative to the research community discipline), gather all research results in one place, monitor and report the community progress.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL: system complete and qualified

LIFECYCLE STATUS: Beta

TARGET USERS: Research Communities, Researchers, project officers, data source managers

USER VALUE

- Facilitates Research Communities adoption of Open Science publishing principles by supporting artefact publishing tools as-a-Service.

USER BASE: Research Communities participating in the dashboard pilots.

1.14 OpenAIRE ScholeXplorer

<http://www.scholix.org>

ScholExplorer

ScholeXplorer populates and provides access to a graph of relationships between datasets and literature, and between datasets and datasets. Objects and relationships are provided by data sources managed by publishers (e.g. CrossRef), data centers (e.g. DataCite and non-DataCite data archives) and repositories. The Service aggregates links expressed in Scholix format and offers programmatic access (APIs) that allow third-party services to run queries/provision of the links in the graph. Among known consumers the service API accounts for Science Direct,

Scopus, and several data repositories.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL: Actual system proven in operational environment

LIFECYCLE STATUS: Production

TARGET USERS: Content providers (data archives, publishers, publication repositories), Research Infrastructures, researchers

USER VALUE

- Enhancing Linked Open Science.
- Intelligent and contextualized research. Enabling new forms of research impact.

USER BASE

The production service includes: 1.100.000 literature objects, 7.100.000 datasets, 38.400.0000 bi-directional scholix links, from 13000 publishers, 10 data centers, CrossRef, DataCite, and OpenAIRE (November 2018).

2 | USE CASES

2.1 Matchbook: A new recommender service to spark scientific collaboration

How can researchers, in the spirit of open science, move beyond their traditional networks to forge new connections? How can public infrastructures like OpenAIRE further enable open science by bringing the right organizations into partnership to stimulate innovation and address the grand societal challenges? To answer these questions, Know-Center releases Matchbook, a prototype recommender service to spark scientific collaboration, produced in partnership with OpenAIRE.

This novel recommender service builds upon the OpenAIRE scholarly graph to enable organizations to keyword search for organizations with the strongest records of funding and collaboration success from the ever-expanding range of funders included in OpenAIRE. OpenAIRE's information on funders and projects, enhanced with links to open access publications and data, is an invaluable resource that has not yet been fully exploited. Drawing information from OpenAIRE on institutions, projects and funders, Matchbook can help scientific institutions interested in forming consortia to identify potential partners with the exact disciplinary strengths and competences they need, rank them according to their previous success in securing funding, and specify searches according to specific national or international funders or even individual funding streams. The service uses Know-Center's Scalable Recommender Framework to generate recommendations based on three different types of algorithms:

1. **Content-Filtering:** recommends institutions based on keywords given by users. The titles and keywords of all OpenAIRE projects are collected and used to calculate a TF-IDF for each project, which is then used to rank results relative to a user's desired keywords.
2. **Collaborative-Filtering:** calculates recommendations for a given organization (based on its organisation id, for example. Recommendations depend on the project collaboration (algorithm is looking for similar organizations based on common projects). Organization similarity and the probability that an organization will be recommended gets higher with the increase of common projects.
3. **Hybrid-Filtering:** uses a combination of the two previous algorithms to recommend partners which not only fulfil specific keywords but also suit the profile of a given partner.

A provisional demonstrator interface for the service has been developed to showcase the service. Via this interface users can query the service using the three algorithms. Organizations (e.g., funders) can also embed the service in their own websites. The recommender system provides three REST-based Web services (i.e., one service per algorithm) that enable easy customization via GET-parameters (e.g., to set a given partner or keywords). A Swagger-based GUI has been provided for conveniently testing the services and for allowing an easy integration into OpenAIRE

by calling the services via JavaScript. Know-Center has also made our python code used to ingest data from the [OpenAIRE API](#) available for re-use.

Algorithm:
Keyword-Filtering

Keyword:
data science

Funder:
ALL

Number of Recommendations:
10

Get Recommendations

Matchbook demonstrator interface

Matchbook works as a successful proof-of-concept but would require more development before being able to be offered as a standalone production service – in particular, the recommendations are currently made on a relatively scarce dataset (i.e., just project titles and keywords, collaboration histories of institutions but not always individual departments) which means that performance suffers in comparison to similar recommender services based on richer information. A next step in this research would be to add enriched information – perhaps including text-mining of full project descriptions (also to the work-package level) and linking the publications linked to projects.

In addition, more work could be done to:

- Add information to make more the algorithms more transparent and better explain how results were calculated and ranked.
- Develop further use-cases to provide personalized recommendations of individual projects or individuals.
- Adapt algorithms by considering beyond-accuracy objectives such as optimizing recommendation diversity and serendipity.
- Integrate Matchbook with VIPER ([The Visual Project Explorer](#)), created by [Open Knowledge Maps](#). VIPER is a unique open science application that provides overviews of research projects indexed by OpenAIRE. Know-Center is an organizational member of Open Knowledge Maps, and the two organisations collaborate closely together.

This use case has demonstrated that

- OpenAIRE’s information on institutions, projects and funders enhanced with links to open access publications and data was used as a rich source of data.
- This data can be reused and curated to make the algorithms more transparent.
- Institutions interested in forming consortia can identify potential partners with the exact disciplinary strengths and competences.

More information: Based on Matchbook: A new recommender service to spark scientific collaboration blogpost by Tony Ross-Hellauer and Hrvoje Lucić, Know-Center, Graz, Austria (<https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=3743>)

2.2 VIPER: The Visual Project Explorer

VIPER: The Visual Project Explorer

A massive 2.4 million research projects from around the world are listed in the OpenAIRE database. But getting an overview of project outputs can be tedious: you are often faced with lengthy reports and outdated project websites, especially when the project has already finished. This leads to a situation that you probably encountered before – it is almost impossible to get a complete and clear picture of what has been produced in some of the most important projects, and much less to understand the impact of this output.

[VIPER, the Visual Project Explorer](#), addresses this problem. It enables funders, institutions and researchers to systematically explore a project’s output, and to understand its reception in different areas. VIPER was developed by [Open Knowledge Maps](#) with funding received in the scope of the OpenAIRE Tender Calls, and is built on top of OpenAIRE’s massive database of research projects, publications, and datasets. A unique property of OpenAIRE data has been exploited: the link between projects, publications and datasets. This, in turn, enables the developers to realize an innovative open science application.

Overview of **StronGrHEP - Strong Gravity and High-Energy ... (690904)** [more info](#)

111 documents (89 open access) Source: OpenAIRE 111 papers 0 datasets Funder: EC 2016-2019

In VIPER, each project is represented as a knowledge map: a visualization showing a topical clustering of a project's publications and datasets (see above). Users can interact with the visualization by zooming into a particular cluster and inspect the underlying outputs in detail. If a publication is open access, you can even view it within the same interface.

The knowledge map can be scaled according to different metrics, including citation data and altmetrics. This means that the sizes of clusters and outputs are adjusted to reflect the number of times they have been cited, read or tweeted. In that way, VIPER enables users to keep track of the reception of a project in a multifaceted and contextualized way that goes beyond simple aggregate numbers and rankings.

Area: Dynamical formation, Reissner nordström, Synchronised hair

VIPER uses the [OpenAIRE API](#) to retrieve publications and datasets related to a project. These outputs are later enriched with metrics data from [CrossRef](#) and [Altmetric](#) and visualized with the award-winning open source mapping software [Head Start](#). The resulting maps are automatically updated by a processing component that queries the OpenAIRE API at regular intervals.

While VIPER can be used on its own, project representations can also be embedded on other websites, e.g. on project websites or within institutional dashboards using a simple JavaScript snippet. On a project website, the visual representation can be used as an automatically updated dissemination page. In user tests, we also found that VIPER would be a useful tool for organizations to showcase their output and identify resources relevant for research communication. For funders, VIPER could be a way to systematically compare funding input to output.

In the future, it's planned to explore these use cases in more detail and improve VIPER. The plan also includes integrating it further with OpenAIRE services and also with the [Matchbook](#). Also – as some users pointed out – it would be useful to have an editing mode, where project representations can be modified, for example enabling enriching metadata or rearranging map items.

To try out VIPER, please head to <https://openknowledgemaps.org/viper>. Enjoy!

This use case has demonstrated that

- Unique OpenAIRE link between projects, publications and datasets enables interactive knowledge map and visualizations showing a topical clustering of a project's publications and datasets.
- The knowledge map can be scaled according to different metrics, including citation data and altmetrics.
- On a project website, the visual representation can be used as an automatically updated dissemination page. And the reception of a project could be tracked in a multifaceted and contextualized way.

(Based on VIPER: The Visual Project Explorer blogpost by [Open Knowledge Maps](#) at <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=3735>)

2.3 Data2Paper Scholix Integration

'[Data2Paper](#)' is a 'one-click' process to streamline the data paper publication workflow. Metadata about a dataset (together with a link to the dataset itself) are transferred from a data repository, via a cloud-based helper app which allows the addition of methodological detail, to a relevant publisher as a data paper submission. The app leverages DataCite DOI and ORCID functionality to avoid data re-entry, saving time and avoiding errors. If accepted and published, subsequent details of the paper can be fed back to the repository to enrich the original record via ORCID functionality.

Data papers increase the opportunities for citation, improve the reproducibility of science through the dissemination of methodological information and also permit the release of negative results, thereby reducing repeat failures and increasing the efficiency of research resource utilization. Making the publication process as friction-free as possible incentivizes researchers to deposit their data in repositories and through data papers encourage and enable its sharing, verification and re-use. In addition, data papers themselves are first class research outputs.

Part of Jisc's Research Data Spring initiative, Data2Paper is operated by a not-for-profit company [Jemura](#). It has built on work done by the [WDS-RDA Publishing Data Workflow Working Group](#) on

data publishing, run a survey for stakeholders to establish the baseline demand and is building a live end-to-end workflow for testing with real authors, data sets, repositories and journals. Partners for this phase include the University of Manchester, [Mendeley Data](#) and Elsevier with helpful input from [ORCID](#), [Figshare](#), [Project THOR](#) and [SURF](#) as well as expressions of interest from a wide range of publishers and repositories.

Integration details: Scholix for Journal Entries

When a user is selecting which journal or archive to publish with using Data2Paper they have the option of viewing more details about any particular choice. This includes information provided by the publisher/archive host such as Open Access status, policies and licenses, editorial information and relevant APC details. Now, the system will also display the most recent data related articles for that journal culled from the OpenAIRE SCHOLIX hub.

Data in Brief Public Deposited

Data in Brief provides a way for researchers to easily share and reuse each other's datasets by publishing data articles that: * Thoroughly describe your data, facilitating reproducibility. * Make your data, which is often buried in supplementary material, easier to find. * Increase traffic towards associated research articles and data, leading to more citations. * Open up doors for new collaborations. Because you never know what data will be useful to someone else, Data in Brief welcomes submissions that describe data from all research areas.

Last modified: 20/03/2018

Relationships

In Administrative Set: [Default Admin Set](#)

Descriptions

Attribute Name	Values
ISSN / eISSN	2352-3409
Homepage	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/data-in-brief
Resource type	data journal
Publisher	Elsevier
Description	Data in Brief provides a way for researchers to easily share and reuse datasets by publishing data articles that: * Thoroughly describe your reproducibility. * Make your data, which is often buried in supplementary material, easier to find. * Increase traffic towards associated research articles and data, leading to more citations. * Open up doors for new collaborations. Because you never know what data will be useful to someone else, Data in Brief welcomes submissions that describe data from all research areas.
Keywords	Open access

Latest Publications

- Characterization data of githead sea (Sparus aurata) IGF-1 receptors (IGF-1) doi: 10.1016/j.dib.2015.12.046 pbmid: 26904713
- Characterization data of githead sea (Sparus aurata) IGF-1 receptors (IGF-1) doi: 10.1016/j.dib.2015.12.046 pbmid: 26904713
- Data on screening and identification of modified papaya in food supply doi: 10.1016/j.dib.2015.12.046 pbmid: 27626052

Scholix for Workflow Completion

Previously, the Data2Paper workflow ended when an article was submitted. Thereafter, the editorial and publication processes were outside the control of Data2paper so the workflow was left without proper closure. By using SCHOLIX, it's possible to detect when an article has been published in the relevant journal which references the DataCite DOI held by Data2Paper, and thereby flag the article as "published". Equally, if nothing happens after some time, user could be prompted to either chase the journal, or consider modifying the paper and resubmitting

elsewhere. Having this closure also improves data management since the application can, after a suitable period, safely delete successful publication workflows since they will have served their purpose.

(Based on Data2Paper Scholix Integration <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=3740>)

2.4 OpenAIRE APIs and Open Science Management at ISCTE-IUL

ISCTE – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa is a research university with 9000 students enrolled in undergraduate (46%) and postgraduate (54%) programmes, 450 lecturers and eight units performing high-quality research:

- Centre for International Studies [CEI-IUL]
- Centre for International Studies [CIES-IUL]
- Centre for Social Research and Intervention [CIS-IUL]
- Centre for Research in Anthropology [CRIA’s ISCTE-IUL branch]
- Centre for Socioeconomic Change and Territorial Studies [DINÂMIA’CET-IUL]
- Instituto de Telecomunicações-IUL [IT’s ISCTE-IUL branch]
- Information Sciences, Technologies and Architecture Research Center [ISTAR-IUL] and
- Business Research Unit [BRU-IUL]

ISCTE-IUL Documentation and Information Services provide the following Research Information Management services:

- Publications and scholarship expertise;
- Discoverability, access and reputational support;
- Training and support; and
- Stewardship of the institutional record.

ISCTE-IUL Repository in 2017

Projects		Number of deposits
1	CIES-IUL (2013)	238
2	DINÂMIA'CET (2015/17)	146
3	DINÂMIA'CET (2013/14)	104
4	CEI-IUL (2015/17)	79
5	CIS-IUL (2013/14)	56
6	CRIA-IUL (2015/17)	26
7	BRU-IUL (2015/17)	16
8	RESCUE - Patterns of Resilience during Socioeconomic Crises among Households in Europe (2014/17)	10
9	TESS - Transition to an environmentally sustainable energy system (2011/14)	10
10	IT (2015/17)	9

ISCTE-IUL Repository and OpenAIRE, 2017

Data source		Number of publications
1	Universidade do Minho: RepositoriUM	5,649
2	arXiv.org e Print Archive	4,429
3	Europe PubMed Central	4,195
4	DOAJ Articles	2,781
5	Other	2,083
6	Repositório Aberto da Universidade do Porto	2,025
7	Crossref	1,912
8	Estudo Geral	1,867
9	Universidade de Lisboa: Repositório.UL	1,411

10	Repositório Institucional da Universidade de Aveiro	1,179
11	Biblioteca Digital do IPB	1,087
12	Hyper Article en Ligne	626
13	INRIA a CCSD electronic archive server	610
14	Repositório Institucional da Universidade Católica Portuguesa	599
15	UTL Repository	501
16	CORE RIOXX UK Aggregator	443
17	Repositório Científico do Instituto Nacional de Saúde de	426
18	Repositório do ISCTE	409
19	Research Papers in Economics	384
20	Repositório Científico do Instituto Politécnico do Porto	368

ISCTE-IUL Repository and OpenAIRE, 2017

ISCTE-IUL Repository team checked the documents deposited in the ISCTE-IUL Repository with references to projects (2012-2017), added “Funding record” field in Ciência-IUL and used

OpenAIRE Provide services. It has also built awareness, conducted training, produced flyers and launched Ask a Librarian service.

LICENÇAS CREATIVE COMMONS

COPIAR E PARTILHAR ATRIBUINDO AUTORIA	COPIAR E PARTILHAR COM A MESMA LICENÇA, ATRIBUINDO AUTORIA PARA USO NÃO COMERCIAL

IDENTIFICADORES PERSISTENTES

DOI
[HTTP://DX.DOI.ORG/10.1111/PERE.12163](http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/PERE.12163)

HANDLE
[HTTP://HDL.HANDLE.NET/10071/13136](http://hdl.handle.net/10071/13136)

IDENTIFICAÇÃO INSTITUCIONAL

INSTITUTO UNIVERSITÁRIO DE LISBOA (ISCTE-IUL),
UNIDADE DE INVESTIGAÇÃO, LISBOA, PORTUGAL

E-MAIL
A.EXEMPLO@ISCTE-IUL.PT

IDENTIFICAÇÃO DO PROJETO FINANCIADOR

FINANCIAMENTO FCT

BOLSA
SFRH/BD/21665/2005

UNIDADE DE INVESTIGAÇÃO
UID/SOC/03126/2013

FINANCIAMENTO EU

CONTRACT NUMBER
656208

TÍTULO
NEXT GENERATION NANOWIRE SOLAR CELLS

ISCTE-IUL Repository and OpenAIRE, 2018

FCT Publications by project (top 30) *IT and CRIA's ISCTE-IUL branch

FCT Publications by data provider (top 20)

As a result, all these efforts:

- Facilitated the compliance with funder requirements (acknowledgement of EU funding and Normas de Informação e Publicitação de Apoios para Beneficiários da FCT);
- Increased the number of deposits in open access;
- Increased dissemination and visibility of scientific production in a European e-Infrastructure; and
- Facilitated evaluation of Research Units (by FCT, every five years).

ISCTE-IUL repository provides a useful information on open science management:

- Reports;
- Statistics at the macro level (Repository) and micro (projects);
- Possibility of enriching the metadata of the ISCTE-IUL Repository;
- Transparency in science.

More information about ISCTE-IUL Research Information Management is available in Boavida, C. P., Dias, J. & Amante, M. J. (2018). “Research information management at ISCTE-IUL the library’s role”. In *Digital Infrastructures for Research 2018*. Lisboa. <http://hdl.handle.net/10071/16619>.

(Based on [OpenAIRE & Science Management: example of ISCTE-IUL](#) by João Dias)

2.5 Tracking, reporting, monitoring: FWF – Austrian Science Fund

The Austrian Science Fund (FWF), which is Austria's main funding organisation for basic research, encourages and helps all project leaders and project staff members to make their peer-reviewed research results freely available online. Since 1 January 2016, open access has been mandatory for all peer-reviewed publications listed in final reports on FWF-funded projects. Any exceptions must be clearly indicated and justified. For projects that started after 1 January 2015, open access has been compulsory for all peer-reviewed publications.

OpenAIRE includes 16,073 publications from 4,126 FWF-funded projects (from a total of 14,430 projects). 15,722 publications (97%) are open access, one is available in restricted access and there are no publications under embargoed access.

OpenAIRE provides the following statistics to FWF:

FWF publications by access mode

Created by OpenAIRE via HighCharts

1,870 publications are available in open access journals and 14,403 publications in repositories.

FWF green and gold publications

over time

Created by OpenAIRE via HighCharts

FWF publications as outcomes

FWF publications

Top 30 projects in publications

BAR GRAPH | TABLE

from OpenAIRE via HighCharts (date: 8/1/2019)

The FWF conducts an annual monitoring of Open Access policy compliance and publishes the results [online](#). Since 2013, a monitoring of the publication costs financed through the "Peer-Reviewed Publications" and "Stand-Alone Publications" programmes is also carried out and published [online](#).

2.6 Open, interoperable and reproducible neuroinformatics with Research Community Dashboard

The Research Community Dashboard (RCD) is currently in beta <https://beta.connect.openaire.eu>, ready to be released.

The Neuroinformatics RCD is represented by the members of the France Life Imaging (FLI) collaboration. FLI focuses on e-infrastructure services to enable interoperability between in-vivo image acquisition platforms at national and international levels (EGI), use OpenAIRE services and promote their adoption across neuroinformatics scientists by generating and sharing packages of research artefacts.

Users can search publications, data, software and other research products, and projects.

Research community members could easily upload and share their research output in Zenodo or locate and use other repositories for open outputs sharing; and link their projects, publications and research data.

Monitoring tools provide publications, research data, software and other research products statistics through the years, as well as overview by access mode and projects highlights.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo community page for Neuroinformatics. At the top left is a brain icon. The title "Neuroinformatics" is centered. On the right, there are navigation links: SEARCH, MONITOR, SHARE, and LINK, along with a yellow "Subscribe" button. Below the title, a list of tags includes brain mapping, brain imaging, electroencephalography, arterial spin labelling, brain fingerprinting, brain, neuroimaging, Multimodal Brain Image Analysis, fMRI, and neuroinformatics (selected), with a "show more" link. Below the tags, it says "Curated by: sorina.pop, camille.maumet, christian.barillot" and "Created: 21-11-2018 Members: 11 Zenodo communities: 1". A statistics section shows: 22,887 publications, 3,837 research data, 78 software, 2,681 other research products, 9 projects, and 6 content providers. The "Recent research results" section has tabs for publications (selected), research data, software, and other research products. A "View all" link is on the right. A featured article is titled "Challenges in the analysis of massive, multimodal, neurodevelopmental data" by Roberto Toro (2018), with an "OPEN" button.

Publications through the years

Publications by access mode

Publications per project

Research data through the years

Research data by access mode

Software through the years

Software by access mode

Other Research products per project

For resources sharing, FLI uses an open source web platform for sharing neuro-imaging resources [Shanoir](#) and Virtual Imaging Platform (VIP).

<https://vip.creatis.insa-lyon.fr>

Virtual Imaging Platform (VIP)

Web portal

Application as a service
File transfer to/from grid

Scientific applications

Cancer therapy simulation

Prostate radiotherapy plan simulated with GAT (L. Grevillot and D. Sarut)

Neuro-image analysis

Brain tissue segmentation with FreeSurfer

Image simulation

Echocardiography simulated with FIELD-II (O. Bernard et al)

Modeling and optimization of distributed computing systems

Acceleration yielded by non-claimant task replication (R. Ferreira da Silva et al)

Infrastructure

Supported by EGI Infrastructure
Uses biomed VO (~65 sites in Europe and beyond)
230 cumulated CPU years utilized by VIP applications in 1 year

 EGI
 France-Grilles
 DIRAC

Users

1000+ registered users in October 2018
44 publications since 2011

VIP and Shanoir will become providers/repositories from which OpenAIRE will harvest software (Boutiques pipelines, Dockers, etc.) and data. [Boutiques](#) – a cross-platform descriptive command-line framework for applications – implements “bosh publish” of neuroinformatics software descriptors to Zenodo with support for tags and Zenodo provides DOIs.

Neuroinformatics RCD gathers and facilitates search for all kind of research artefacts from the neuroinformatics community: literature, datasets, software; links datasets and software to articles; publish artefacts automatically and directly from data storage and computing platforms and enable open, interoperable and reproducible science.

(Based on [The Neuroinformatics community in OpenAIRE Connect](#) by Sorina Pop, Axel Bonnet, Camille Maumet, Michael Kain, Christian Barillot and Tristan Glatard)

2.7 Enabling open science publishing for Research

Infrastructures: The EPOS use-case

Research infrastructures (RI) are “system of systems”, providing services and good practices, safeguarding technology standards, bringing economy of scale, and often are mature enough to support reproducibility of science by keeping different forms of research objects. Still, often, such research objects are not published as scientific products. Publishing is limited to articles, possibly associated to datasets, and rarely to software.

OpenAIRE Research Community Dashboard (RCD) offers a solution with minimal efforts for RIs and without renouncing any of their services or current practices. It provides RIs with scholarly communication services for discovery and publishing of an interlinked graph of articles, datasets, software, and other products, including research objects. Scientists in a RI can delegate their RCD to aggregate all scientific products pertaining their RI, classifying them as one the

aforementioned types, and identify semantic links between such products. Most importantly, the RI services can interact with the RCD to deposit scientific products, hence publish them as scholarly communication first-citizens, with attribution/citation metadata and a DOI.

The European Plate Observing System (EPOS) – a pan-European distributed RI for solid Earth science – integrates its service EPOSAR in an open science publishing workflow with RCD. Through the integration of national research infrastructures and data, EPOS helps scientists to make a step change in developing new geo-hazards and geo-resources concepts and Earth science applications to address key societal challenges.

CNR-IREA is an Italian service provider of EPOS with a portfolio of satellite Earth Observation services aimed at generating value-added products for Solid Earth applications and natural disaster analysis, prevention and mitigation. EPOS scientists benefit from the on-demand EPOSAR service that implements an advanced Differential Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) Interferometry (DInSAR) technique, referred to as Parallel Small Baseline Subset (P-SBAS) approach, to detect Earth surface displacements with sub-centimetre accuracy. The P-SBAS approach allows the generation of surface deformation time series and velocity maps by processing in a parallel and efficient way SAR dataset consisting of tens or hundreds of images acquired over the same investigated area. EPOSAR outputs are extremely effective to investigate natural (earthquakes, volcanic unrests, landslides) and/or man-made (tunneling excavations, aquifer exploitation, oil and gas storage and extraction, infrastructures monitoring) hazards.

EPOSAR can be accessed via the ESA's Geohazards Exploitation Platform (GEP) <https://tep.eo.esa.int/> that transparently offers scalable and parallel processing/analysis tools over pre-loaded satellite big datasets. Scientists can integrate their applications, i.e. analysis algorithms/chains like P-SBAS above for EPOSAR, and make them available as-a-service through the GEP geo-browser to other scientists.

The community (beyond EPOS) has no specific best practices yet on how to deposit and cite the datasets resulting from EPOSAR or other EPOS services. A few journals have recently started to require the deposition of datasets in a data repository, but in general data is embedded in the article as an image or a table. This makes the overall degree of FAIR-ness and reproducibility in EPOS very low: datasets are often not shared as independent scientific products, provenance of datasets is not provided, and the experimental tools are not shared.

CNR-IREA integrates its EPOS services with the RCD in order to ensure publishing of research products and experiments in a way that supports their use, reuse and reproducibility. As a first step, scientists identify, interlink, and claim products relevant to the EPOS community. Secondly, the EPOSAR Graphical User Interface will be modified in order to let the user decide if to publish an experiment and relative results, thereby implementing a “on-demand publishing” workflow.

Finally, to this aim, GEP will be equipped with a publishing component capable of fetching experiment and dataset information from the local databases, package them as products as required by Zenodo and deposit them via APIs on behalf of the EPOSAR authorized service under the EPOS community. More specifically, the publishing component generates for each experiment the two research products:

- A Zenodo “other product” of type “research object” relative to the experiment, encoded as a machine readable file;
- A Zenodo “datasets” relative to the output displacement time series or the velocity maps, consisting of the files described in the previous section.

Such products will be reciprocally interlinked, have their own DOI, given citation metadata, semantics links with other products if needed, and, as a consequence of being deposited in Zenodo under the EPOS community, be discoverable/browsable through the EPOS RCD. It is of course up to the users to opt when their experiment is mature enough to be published in OpenAIRE as a citable and preserved experiment object, and eventually cite the object from any articles they may produce.

More information about open science publishing with EPOSAR in EPOS including an overview of technical efforts is provided in this conference paper: Manghi, Paolo, Manunta, Michele, Baglioni, Miriam, Bardi, Alessia, Casu, Francesco, De Luca, Claudio, & Kokogiannaki, Argiro. (2018). Enabling Open Science publishing for Research Infrastructures via OpenAIRE: The EPOS use-case. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1412509>.

2.8 The research life-cycle made easy using OpenAIRE and EOSC-hub services: Making data open yet anonymous

Becky is an early career social scientist. She is excited to have been offered a competitive post in a well-established department to work on an international Horizon 2020 funded five year research project with many partners. The project started a year before she arrived, and her institution leads the research on the language used to describe immigration in the national press.

Data Everywhere

Becky knows that a significant amount of research data has already been gathered during interviews with desk editors. This research data is safely stored in a closed cloud computing area on the secure TSD – Service for Sensitive Data service. TSD is a cloud computing platform designed to comply with the security regulations appropriate to handle sensitive data. This service is provided through the [Hub](#).

Having the data safely and securely stored via the TSD service means that only the authorized researchers have access to it. The data has limited accessibility, is not discoverable and cannot be easily shared with other researchers. This is why the ‘FAIRness’ of the data is rather poor.

In her second week, Becky receives a reminder from the project’s coordinator that their H2020 Data Management Plan (DMP) is due for update. She needs to find out two things:

1. How to update the data management plan – about which she has little experience and;
2. How to comply with the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data mandate.

Becky’s University European Office had previously given her information about the [OpenAIRE Helpdesk](#). The OpenAIRE Helpdesk is where all the researchers participating in Horizon 2020 funded projects can benefit from personal assistance from a range of experts to make their data discoverable and accessible to others. This includes recommendations for making them FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) and drafting the DMP. The DMP is important, since it allows the funder to check whether the project’s research is managed according to the funding agreement. Becky is directed to [a suite of materials about mandate compliance](#) that can help her understand the benefits of open data and why sharing the project data outcomes far and wide is good for society, the project itself and her research field.

But Is the Data Shareable?

According to the DMP, every time a dataset is included in a publication, it needs to be publicly available to comply to the FAIR principles. Since the dataset contains sensitive information, Becky first needs to anonymize personal information from the people interviewed.

Her concern about the sensitiveness of the data is reinforced by an email from her university's ethics department reminding her to check the status of personal data and the need to conform to [GDPR principles](#). Realizing that much of the project data is sensitive, Becky goes back to the OpenAIRE Helpdesk to guide her through the different options.

An Anonymous Solution

The helpdesk proposes [AMNESIA](#), a tool developed by OpenAIRE to support researchers to anonymize their research data. AMNESIA is a flexible data anonymization tool that allows to remove identifying information from data. It removes direct identifiers like names, SSNs etc., but also transforms secondary identifiers like birth date and zip code so that individuals cannot be identified in the data.

Private Enough – Open to All

Now that the dataset is anonymized, Becky makes it available and discoverable, by uploading it to [B2SHARE](#) — a data repository provided via the Hub. With B2SHARE, researchers and communities can publish datasets and get Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to use in publications. All datasets published in B2SHARE are automatically made discoverable and findable via [B2FIND](#) — an EUDAT metadata discovery portal that allows users to find data collections within an international and inter-disciplinary scope.

After a few months, Becky discovers that the dataset has been cited on a number of occasions by other researchers and she can see via the download statistics maintained within the B2SHARE service (showing the number of downloads) that objects within the dataset has been downloaded frequently.

The Outcome: Thanks to OpenAIRE and EOSC-hub services, Becky was able to get on-the-spot support to make research open for the benefit of all, making sure that her data is well-managed with a management plan, safely stored and published, complying at the same time with GDPR requirements.

(Based on Published or Private: How to do both? The research life-cycle made easy using OpenAIRE and EOSC-hub services: making data open yet anonymous available at <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=3114>)

2.9 Collaborations made easy using OpenAIRE and EOSC-hub services: HADDOCK and Zenodo

Alice and Bob are two structural biologists working on the same field in opposite parts of the world. Alice is a post-doc in a European University, while Bob is setting up a research group in a South American institute. They meet during the poster session of a major scientific conference and, after discovering a common interest in how antibiotics attach to harmful bacteria by binding to the proteins in their membranes, they decide to start working together.

Bob is sitting on a lot of experimental data but has no access to the compute capacity required to analyze the results. Using just his laptop would take months to go through the first simulations. Alice suggests [HADDOCK](#), a web portal that offers computational tools for structural biologists to model the structure of complexes of proteins and other biomolecules.

HADDOCK is one of the thematic services available in the EOSC-hub catalogue, developed by the University of Utrecht and powered by the compute resources of the EGI Federation. HADDOCK is regularly used by thousands of researchers across the world, and most of them won't know their calculations are processed via High-Throughput Compute: the web portal hides all the complexity behind a user-friendly interface, allowing them to focus on the research instead of IT.

While Bob works on the calculations, Alice opens her account in [Zenodo](#) and sets up a community for the project with Bob. Zenodo is an online repository developed by OpenAIRE and CERN, open to all researchers regardless of funding stream, geographical location or scientific field. Free to upload and free to access, Zenodo makes scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable and discoverable for the long term.

The end goal is to have their research and data published in open access to comply with their funders' requirements. But for the moment, while they are working on the project, Bob uploads both the data and the methods he used opting for a restricted access option. This will allow him to share embargoed data with Alice during the paper preparation with the restrictions they need at this stage.

Zenodo Repository
 “Catch-all” repository: OpenAIRE-CERN joint effort

- Multiple data types
 - Publications
 - Long tail of research data
- Citable data (DOI)
- Links to funding, pubs, data, software

API INTEGRATE YOUR APP VIA PROGRAMMABLE API

COMMUNITIES YOUR DIGITAL REPOSITORY ON ZENODO.

FUNDING INTEGRATE INTO REPORTING FOR RESEARCH FUNDED BY EUROPEAN COMMISSION.

FLEXIBLE LICENSING NOT EVERYTHING IS UNDER CREATIVE COMMONS

www.zenodo.org

H2020: Option to gather, preserve and share project's scientific output

Zenodo Features

Zenodo also assigns a DOI, a persistent identifier, to all datasets and method software, as well as specifying the funders and the specific grants that funded this research. This means that when their paper is submitted they can share a protected link to the DOIs with editors and reviewers. And once the paper is accepted for publication, all that Alice and Bob have to do is set the access rights to “embargoed” and enter the publication date, and then Zenodo will automatically toggle the data and methods to open access on that date to make them public and reusable. Moreover, funders, as well as the coordinators of the projects funding this research, will be able to verify the impact of the grant. Finally, and most importantly, other scientists will be able to reuse Bob and Alice’s work, and Bob and Alice will see their scientific reward blossom also based on usage and citation of their data and methods.

EOSC-hub and OpenAIRE-Advance support researchers across the world in many ways. For Alice and Bob, this means:

- Months-worth of computations completed in a couple of days;
- Safe space to share data without risks;
- An effortless way to comply with Open Access requirements.

(Based on Advancing research together: EOSC-hub and OpenAIRE available at <https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=3293>)

3 | NEXT STEPS

Current use cases will be published on the OpenAIRE portal <https://www.openaire.eu/use-cases> and a social media campaign will be launched to collect more use cases. Users will be asked to answer the following questions:

- ✓ Why and how you did you start using OpenAIRE service(s)?
- ✓ How do you integrate OpenAIRE service(s) in your workflow? Explain your workflow if needed.
- ✓ What is the added value? How does it benefit you?
- ✓ Your quote about the use of OpenAIRE services
- ✓ Do you have any feedback about the service(s)? Would you like to suggest any service(s) improvements?

Hope they will serve as good practice examples for others who would like to integrate OpenAIRE services in their workflows.

The screenshot shows the OpenAIRE website's 'Use cases' page. The header includes the OpenAIRE logo and navigation links: SERVICES, SUPPORT, OPEN SCIENCE IN EUROPE, ABOUT, and SIGN IN. The main heading is 'Use cases of OpenAIRE services for different stakeholders'. Below this, a paragraph explains that use case narratives with scenarios of Open Science services are being prepared, targeting researchers, research communities, research infrastructures, content providers, funders, and managers of research. It states the main goal is to showcase how OpenAIRE services contribute to embedding Open Science into researchers' daily workflows and aligning with Open Science policies and infrastructures across European research institutions. A final paragraph mentions that benefits and assumptions of current users and best practices on Open Access publishing, data sharing, and repository enrichment will be available. At the bottom, there is a 'Stay tuned!' icon.

www.openaire.eu/use-cases